

1 **Xist interacts with Alkbh3.**

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6 We measured total transcription in cells in concert with N1-methyladenosine (m1A) profiling, in cells with
7 intact Alkbh3 and in cells lacking Alkbh3. We report here interaction of the non-coding RNA Xist with
8 Alkbh3.

9 Citations

10 1. Safra, M., Sas-Chen, A., Nir, R., Winkler, R., Nachshon, A., Bar-Yaacov, D., Erlacher, M.,
11 Rossmannith, W., Stern-Ginossar, N. and Schwartz, S., 2017. The m1A landscape on cytosolic and
12 mitochondrial mRNA at single-base resolution. Nature, 551(7679), pp.251-255.

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